

Figure S1: The inhibition zones of plant extract against multi-drug resistant bacterial (*Shigella flexneri* Isolate 5 and isolate 8)

Figure S2: The inhibition zones of plant extract against multi-drug resistant bacterial (*Salmonella enterica* Isolates and isolate 5).

Figure S3. Gel electrophoresis of *S. enterica* isolates 16S rRNA gene fragments. The image illustrates the successful amplification of the target gene. Band positions are indicated in base pairs (bp) as compared to the DNA molecular weight marker (L).

Figure S4. Gel electrophoresis of *S. flexneri* 16S rRNA gene fragments. The image illustrates the successful amplification of the target gene. Band positions are indicated in base pairs (bp) as compared to the DNA molecular weight marker (L).

ELx808
Ultra Microplate Reader
BIO-TEK INSTRUMENTS, INC.

Assay: Quick Read Date: 12/05/25 Lot: Operator: Plate ID:
Wavelength: 630 Time: 12:13:57PM Plate ID:

COMMENTS

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
CALL	0.104	0.102	0.100	0.102	0.102	0.104	0.105	0.103	0.105	0.109	0.111	0.109
CALL	0.101	0.101	0.101	0.101	0.101	0.101	0.101	0.101	0.101	0.101	0.101	0.101
CALL	0.100	0.107	0.106	0.108	0.101	0.101	0.102	0.105	0.105	0.107	0.108	0.104
CALL	0.116	0.101	0.107	0.105	0.102	0.108	0.115	0.100	0.106	0.111	0.107	0.105
CALL	0.132	0.135	0.131	0.134	0.130	0.135	0.138	0.134	0.138	0.132	0.134	0.131
CALL	0.131	0.134	0.139	0.135	0.144	0.135	0.138	0.135	0.141	0.145	0.139	0.142
CALL	0.138	0.143	0.141	0.138	0.140	0.138	0.133	0.140	0.131	0.130	0.131	0.131
CALL	0.121	0.118	0.120	0.124	0.117	0.121	0.114	0.121	0.121	0.121	0.124	0.121
CALL	0.163	0.158	0.157	0.168	0.154	0.160	0.171	0.170	0.171	0.171	0.171	0.165

Figure S5: Bio film and Antibiofilm activity

Figure S6. Representative images of preliminary qualitative phytochemical screening tests performed on *Platanus orientalis* methanolic leaf extract, including alkaloid-detecting reagent, terpene, glycoside, flavonoid, carbohydrate, tannin, and phenol tests. These assays are indicative and do not provide definitive identification of individual compounds.

Table S1: The Inhibition zone of different concentration of crude Plant methanolic extract against the *Salmonella entrica* isolates

<i>Salmonella entrica</i>	500	250	125	Mean	SD
Isolate 1 (soil)	20	16	11	15.667	4.509
Isolate 2 (water)	21	15	12	16	4.583
Isolate 3 (water)	18	14	13	15	2.646
Isolate 4 (water)	20	16	12	16	4
Isolate 5	19	15	13	15.667	3.055
Isolate 6	18	15	12	15	3
Isolate 7	20	16	13	16.333	3.512
Isolate 8	19	17	12	16	3.606

Table S2: The Inhibition zone of different concentration of crude Plant methanolic extract against the *Shigella flexneri* isolates

<i>Shigella flexneri</i> Isolate	500	250	125	Mean	SD
Isolate 1	20	15	12	15.66666667	4.041451884
Isolate 2	20	19	12	17	4.358898944
Isolate 3	19	14	12	15	3.605551275
Isolate 4	21	15	12	16	4.582575695
Isolate 5	17	14	12	14.33333333	2.516611478
Isolate 6 (soil)	17	14	12	14.33333333	2.516611478
Isolate 7 (water)	20	14	12	15.33333333	4.163331999
Isolate 8 (water)	19	14	11	14.66666667	4.041451884

Primers:

Salmonella enterica

16sSA F GTGAGTAATGTCTGGGAAACTGC 23

16sSA R ATTCACATCCGACTTGACAGAC 23

Annealing 59 product 522

Shigella flexneri

16sSH F TTGCGTAGAGATCTGGAGGAATA 23

16sSH R GGACTTAACCCAACATTTCAAA 23

Annealing 57 product 402

The image shows a screenshot of the NCBI (National Center for Biotechnology Information) website homepage. At the top, there is a browser address bar with 'ncbi.nlm.nih.gov' and a search bar with a 'Search' button. Below the search bar is a navigation menu with 'All Databases' and a search input field. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- NCBI Home**: A vertical list of resource categories including 'Resource List (A-Z)', 'All Resources', 'Chemicals & Bioassays', 'Data & Software', 'DNA & RNA', 'Domains & Structures', 'Genes & Expression', 'Genetics & Medicine', 'Genomes & Maps', 'Homology', 'Literature', 'Proteins', 'Sequence Analysis', 'Taxonomy', 'Training & Tutorials', and 'Variation'.
- Welcome to NCBI**: A central section with the text 'The National Center for Biotechnology Information advances science and health by providing access to biomedical and genomic information.' and links for 'About the NCBI | Mission | Organization | NCBI News & Blog'.
- Submit**: A section with the text 'Deposit data or manuscripts into NCBI databases' and an icon of an upward arrow.
- Download**: A section with the text 'Transfer NCBI data to your computer' and a downward arrow icon.
- Learn**: A section with the text 'Find help documents, attend a class or watch a tutorial' and a book icon.
- Develop**: A section with the text 'Use NCBI APIs and code libraries to build applications' and a server rack icon.
- Analyze**: A section with the text 'Identify an NCBI tool for your data analysis task' and a network diagram icon.
- Research**: A section with the text 'Explore NCBI research and collaborative projects' and a microscope icon.
- Popular Resources**: A list of links including PubMed, Bookshelf, PubMed Central, BLAST, Nucleotide, Genome, SNP, Gene, Protein, and PubChem.
- NCBI News & Blog**: A section with news items such as 'BankIt Submitters: Upcoming Changes to How You Submit to GenBank' (dated 27 Jan 2026) and 'GenBank Now Supports EGAPx-Based Annotation' (dated 14 Jan 2026).

Primer3Plus pick primers from a DNA sequence		More...	Source Code
		Help	About

[Load server settings:](#) Select primer pairs to detect the given template sequence. Optionally targets and included/excluded regions can be specified.

[Task:](#)

[Sequence Id:](#)

[Paste template sequence below](#) or upload sequence file: No file chosen

Mark selected region:

[Excluded Regions:](#) < >

[Targets:](#) []

[Included Region:](#) { }

[Primer overlap positions:](#) -

[Pair OK Region List:](#)

[Pick left primer](#)
 [Pick hybridization probe](#)
 [Pick right primer](#)